

Protocol of Image Analysis -

Step-by-step instructional guide using the software Fiji, Ilastik and Drishti

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1. Installation

The open-source software Fiji, Ilastik and Drishti are needed in order to perform image analysis as described in this protocol. Install the software for each program on your system, using the html-addresses below.

- In your web browser, open the Fiji homepage for downloads:
<https://fiji.sc/#download>. Select the software option suited for your operating system and download it.
- In your web browser, open the Ilastik homepage for 'Download':
<https://www.ilastik.org/download.html>.
For this work, Ilastik version 1.3.2 was installed, as it was the most recent version. Select the Download option suited for your operating system and follow the download instructions on the webpage.
- In your web browser, open the Drishti page on Github:
<https://github.com/nci/drishti/releases>. Select the versions for your operating system and download 'Drishti version 2.6.3', 'Drishti version 2.6.4' and 'Drishti version 2.6.5'.

2. Pre-processing

Firstly, reduce the size of the CR.2-files from your camera, if the image files are exceedingly large. There is a trade-off between image resolution and both computation time and feasibility. Identify your necessary minimum image resolution and compress your image files to the largest extent possible, for instance by converting them to JPG-files. Large image data may cause the software to crash, if your internal memory capacity is too small.

Secondly, convert your image files to inverted 8-bit grayscale JPG-files and adjust the parameter brightness and contrast to enhance the distinguishability of structures.

The software used for conversion and contrast adjustment was GIMP, but the same results can be achieved with most free photo editing software for image processing such as Krita. However, Fiji cannot be recommended for contrast adjustments, as its curve-fitting function only allows for adjustments using a linear curve, which has proven to create a smaller distinguishability of structures than an S-shape curve.

Once you have pre-processed your image data in terms of size, color and contrast, you need to measure the pixel size and then crop them to the desired size.

- Open Fiji.
- Click on the tab *File > Open*.
- Browse the directory and choose an image file of your dataset in which the photographic reference scale is clearly visible, then click on the 'Open'-button.
- Use the mouse-wheel or [+] on your keyboard to zoom to the photographic reference scale in the image.
- Select the Rectangle-tool on the left side of the toolbar in the Fiji-interface and draw a rectangle of zero width (yellow straight line) between the two centers of two markings.

The height of the rectangle is expressed as 'h' in the Fiji interface (red circle) and represents the length of one millimeter in your image in pixels.

Repeat this step for different markings in the image and for different images. The distance should always be the same number of pixels. Note your measurement before proceeding with cropping your image stack.

Crop the image files to your desired size, invert them and save them as an image stack and as single image files.

- Open Fiji.
- Click on the tab *File > Import > Image sequence*.
- Browse the directory and choose the folder which contains your images.

- Left click on the first image, then click the 'OK'-button. The dialogue box 'Sequence Options' pops up, showing you the overall number of images contained in your folder.

You may change this number, if you need a smaller stack. The resulting stack consists of as many images as you have chosen, starting from the number you assigned as 'Starting image' in the second box.

Check the box 'Convert to 8-bit Grayscale', if you open an image sequence, that has not yet been converted.

If you forget to check this box, you can always convert the images in the stack to 8-bit grayscale images by clicking on the tab *Image > Type > 8bit*.

A dialogue box will pop up, asking whether the conversion should be applied on the entire stack. Click the 'OK'-button to confirm.

- Click the 'OK'-button to open the images as an image stack in Fiji.
- Press [Enter] to move the Fiji interface in front of all open images.
- Left click on the Rectangle-button on the left side of the toolbox in the Fiji interface and draw a rectangular selection in your image stack with your mouse cursor. Use the mouse wheel to move back and forth through your stack to choose the right selection.

the tab *Image > Crop* to crop the entire stack to the size of your current selection or use [ctrl] + [shift] + [X] on your keyboard for the same operation.

- Click on the tab *Edit > Invert* or press [ctrl]+[shift]+[I] on your keyboard to invert the images in your stack.

The dialogue box 'Process Stack?' pops up, asking whether all images in the stack should be processed. Confirm by clicking on the 'Yes'-button.

- Click on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff* to save the image stack as a TIFF-file.

To save your image stack as separate image files in one folder, click on the tab *File > Save As > Image Sequence*.

A dialogue box opens up, enabling you to choose your file format for the single images.

Choose 'TIFF' for Format.

Check the box 'Use slice labels as file names' to keep the names of the images you were using for your image stack.

Alternatively, keep the box unchecked as in the default setting, thereby creating single image files named after your stack name and a consecutive number (e.g. starting with 'my_stack_0000').

You may also change the name of your stack in the second box for this purpose.

Click on the 'OK-button' to confirm your settings.

- A dialogue box opens up that enables you to choose your directory. Click 'Save' to save your images as either a TIFF-stack or as single TIFF-files.

Box 1. - Import into Fiji

There are different options available to open image-files in Fiji.

1. Drag&Drop:

Choose one or more image files and drag them to the lower bar of the Fiji interface while pressing your left mouse button, until "Drag&Drop" appears on the interface. Release the left mouse button and all images are opened in separate windows in Fiji.

To convert all open images to an image stack, click on the tab *Image > Stacks > Images to Stack*.

However, Fiji does not necessarily array the images in the same order as the images were saved in your folder. Oftentimes when you use Drag&Drop, the last image is being placed as the first slice of the stack.

Slices currently displayed can be deleted from the stack by clicking on the tab *Image > Stacks > Delete Slice*.

2. Open single image or image stack:

Click on the tab *File > Open* to open a single file (image file or image stack). A window opens in which you can browse your directory. Choose the file by clicking on it and open the file by clicking the 'Open'-button.

To avoid browsing through your directory repeatedly, you can also open files you recently worked with in Fiji by clicking on the header *File > Open Recent* and choose your file as a shortcut to the directory path.

3. Import files:

Click on the tab *File > Import* and choose from a variety of file formats the specific format you want to open. With 'Image sequence' you can import single files and open them directly as an image stack.

3. Semi-Automatic Segmentation

For carrying out semi-automatic segmentation of components in your image files in Fiji, it is likely that Fiji requires more internal memory access to function correctly. Increase the memory capacity that Fiji may use, by setting it slightly below your computer's random-access-memory (RAM).

- Open Fiji.
- Click on the tab *Edit > Options > Memory&Threads*.
- A dialogue box opens, displaying your current maximum memory. Increase the number of megabytes for 'Maximum Memory', then click the 'OK'-button.

- Restart Fiji to have the changes for maximum memory applied.

Before segmenting the image data, adjust Fiji's update site to allow the segmentation plugin to function.

- Click on the tab *Help > Update* to update Fiji. A dialogue box pops up showing the progress of the search for new updates. It closes by itself. Subsequently, the interface for the 'ImageJ Updater' opens in a new window.

If your version of Fiji is updated already, a dialogue box opens up to communicate this information. Click 'OK' to close it. If there are new updates available, they are shown in the interface.

- Click on the button 'Manage Update Sites' on the left.

- The 'Manage update sites' dialogue box opens showing a list of different applications. Check the box for 'ImageScience', then click the 'Close'-button. Again, a dialogue box opens showing the search progress for new updates related to the 'ImageScience' library.

- Update Fiji by clicking on the 'Apply Changes' button. To apply the updates, restart Fiji.

The image data is segmented using the Fiji plugin 'Trainable WEKA Segmentation'. Before segmenting the all image files, use a small sample from the single image files to test for different filters and settings and determine which may fit your objective best.

If your image data is heterogeneous, choose a small number of image files (3-10), that represent the entire range of your image data and convert them to an image stack.

- Open Fiji.
- Use Drag&Drop to open your image files.
- Click on the tab *Image > Stacks > Images to Stack*.
- Click on the tab *Plugins > Segmentation > Trainable WEKA Segmentation* to open the plugin in a new window.
- Click on the button 'Create new class' in the interface of the plugin to create an additional class to the two default classes and name it.
- Click on the 'Settings'-button to open the window 'Segmentation Settings'.

Change the name of the existing classes by changing the 'Class names'.

Choose your filters by checking and unchecking the boxes for 'Training features'.

Adjust Membrane thickness, Membrane patch size, Minimum sigma and Maximum sigma to your desired values.

Keep the default settings for everything else.

Click the 'OK'-button to confirm the new settings.

- Use the mouse wheel or the scrollbar on the bottom of the window to navigate through your image stack and switch from one image to another.
To zoom in and out of an image, press [ctrl] on your keyboard while using the mouse wheel.
- Label an area in the image by tracing it with the mouse and then clicking the button 'Add to class X' on the right side. The trace appears in the box below its class.

It is not necessary to fill a distinctive structure in your image with traces. A single trace within is sufficient. Edge areas are often difficult to classify, therefore it improves the performance of the algorithm, if traces are added in such areas, where structures are difficult to distinguish.

- Select a trace by left-clicking on it. Now can be relocated the image with the mouse by dragging it to a different place in the image.
- Delete a trace by double-clicking on it.
- Not all structures in each image need to be traced. Few traces on structures, which display the properties for the classes well, may suffice. The plugin works well even with less than twenty traces.

- Click the button 'Train classifier' on the left side, if you have placed your traces.

Now the plugin is starting to calculate the classes for each pixel in the images stack. Depending on the size of the system's internal memory and the size of the input data, the process will take several minutes to be complete.

- Turn off the overlaying class predictions by clicking on the button 'Toggle overlay' on the left side.
- Check the image stack for false class predictions and add new traces to correct for them. Click 'Train classifier' again and repeat this step until the class predictions are suitable.

- Click the 'Create result'-button to create a segmented image stack that consists only of the predicted classes.
- Create a probability map by clicking on the 'Get probability'-button on the left side, to compute an image stack that displays the likelihood of pixels belonging to a class through color intensity.

It will be displayed as white or red pixels for your first class on a black background and simultaneously as white or red pixels for your second class on a black background, by combining two stacks in one window. You can switch from one stack to the other by moving the first bar at the bottom of the window from left to right.

Save the probability maps as a TIFF-stack by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff* in the Fiji interface.

Fiji is then saving the one 'probability maps'-stack, which is currently visible in your window. You may either save both stacks or save only one stack and later invert it by clicking on the tab

- Save the current settings as classifiers by clicking the 'Save classifier'-button on the left.

To compare different settings and test for the best set of filters, they need to be tested on the small sample stack.

- Note your settings for each test and save the output as described above.
- Change the segmentation settings and use different filters and different values for 'Membrane thickness', 'Membrane patch size', 'Minimum sigma' and 'Maximum sigma'. Then train the classifiers again.
- While tracing during testing, try to place the traces always on the same structures in your images, to increase the comparability of the different settings.

- Compare all the outputs and choose the most fitting set of filters to predict your classes. Most fitting is the set that needs the least manual correction by placing new traces, as there are only few pixels falsely classified.
- Save the selected settings as classifiers by clicking the 'Save classifier'-button on the left. The result is saved as a model-file. This 'classifier.model' can be used to segment the larger image stack later on.

Selected training features for the paper:

Filters: Gaussian blur, Sobel filter, Hessian, Difference of gaussians, Membrane projections and Kuwahara.

Membrane thickness: 1

Membrane patch size: 19

Minimum sigma: 0.5

Maximum sigma: 20.0 for RWSN / 30.0 for RWSS

After selecting a fitting set of classifiers, the complete image data can be segmented.

- Open Fiji.
- Open your pre-processed image data as a TIFF-stack by clicking the tab *File > Import > Image Sequence*.
- Open the plugin 'Trainable WEKA segmentation' by clicking on the tab *Plugins > Segmentation > Trainable WEKA segmentation*.
- Click the button 'Load Classifier' to import your selected classifiers. Choose the file from the directory and click the 'OK'-button.
- Trace objects in the image and add the traces to the classes, then train your classifiers.
- Compute a segmented image stack by clicking on 'Create result'.
- Compute a probability map by clicking on 'Get probability'.
- Create a new folder in your directory, in which you want to save all computed data for your image stack.
- Save the entire project by clicking on 'Save data', choose the new folder from the directory, enter a name and click on the 'OK'-button to save your file.
- In your project's folder, create two new sub-folders for either the probability maps or the classified images to save them in separate places. Save both the 'probability maps'-stack and the 'classified image'-stack as TIFF-stacks by clicking on each of them and then opening the Fiji interface, clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*.
- Additionally, save your image data as single files by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Image Sequence*.

If your image data is too large, you will encounter memory problems when segmenting your image data with the TWS-plugin. Observe CPU usage and memory utilization (e.g. with Windows-Task-Manager) while using the TWS-plugin. The software crashes when reaching 100% in physical memory usage.

However, the segmentation can still be performed. Memory errors can be avoided by running simple scripts provided on the ImageJ-webpage¹, but for this work the image data was too large even for the scripting approach. The image data was divided into smaller image stacks and after segmentation was performed on them, the results were added up to re-form the complete image stack.

To divide your image data and merge the results after segmentation, the image directory on your system needs to be organized accordingly.

- Open Fiji.
- Open the pre-processed image stack by using Drag&Drop.
- Create a smaller substack (e.g. the first 50 images) by clicking on the tab *Image > Stacks > Tools > Make Substack*. The dialogue box 'Substack Maker' opens up.

Enter the range of slices your substack should contain, starting with the slice number of the stack which should be the first slice of your substack (e.g. '1-50' for the first substack, '51-100' for the second substack,...).

Click the 'OK'-button. The new substack will open up in a different window.

- Repeat the last step until all substacks are created.
- Create different folders in your directory and in which the substacks of your pre-processed image data can be saved as image stacks and as single image files. Label the folders accurately.
- Save each substack as a TIFF-stack by clicking on its window and then on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff* in the Fiji interface. Specify the substack's name but keep the range as part of its name, before clicking on the 'Save'-button.
- Save each substack as single image files by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Image Sequence*. Select the correct new folder and click the 'Save'-button. The single image file names are being labeled with the substack's name and a consecutive number (e.g. 'substack(1-50)0000', 'substack(1-50)0001', ...).
- Click on the tab *File > Import > Image sequence*.
- Browse the directory and choose the folder which contains your first substack.
- Check the box 'Convert to 8-bit Grayscale' in the dialogue box 'Sequence Options' then click the 'OK'-button.

1 https://imagej.net/Scripting_the_Trainable_Weka_Segmentation [accessed 03.05.2019, 17:22]

- Save the image sub-stack by clicking the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*. Select the folder with the single images that make up your sub-stack and click the 'Save'-button.
- Open the plugin 'Trainable WEKA segmentation' by clicking on the tab *Plugins > Segmentation > Trainable WEKA segmentation*.
- Click the button 'Load Classifier' to import your selected classifiers from the testing. Choose the file from the directory and click the 'OK'-button.
- Trace objects in the images and add the traces to the classes, then train your classifiers.
- Compute a segmented image stack by clicking on 'Create result'.
- Compute a probability map by clicking on 'Get probability'.
- Create a new folder within the folder for your substack, in which you can save all computed results for the particular sub-stack.
- Save the entire project by clicking on the 'Save data'-button, choose the new folder from the directory and click on the 'OK'-button to save your file.
- In your results-folder for the substack, create two new sub-folders for either the probability maps or the classified images to save them in separate places.
- Save both the 'probability maps'-stack and the 'classified image'-stack as TIFF-stacks by clicking on each of them and then opening the Fiji interface, clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*.

Designate an identical name to each of your resulting sub-stacks and clearly label it with a number (e.g. 'DataX_probability_Stack1', 'DataX_probability_Stack2'). Saving the sub-stacks as single image files in the next step will add a consecutive number to each image (e.g. 'DataX_probability_Stack1_c1', 'DataX_probability_Stack1_c2', ...). This type of labeling allows for copying all single files from all sub-stacks into a single folder while keeping the correct order of the images as in the original stack.

```
DataX_probability_Stack1_c1DataX_classified_Stack1_c1
DataX_probability_Stack1_c2DataX_classified_Stack1_c2
DataX_probability_Stack1_c3DataX_classified_Stack1_c3
DataX_probability_Stack2_c1DataX_classified_Stack2_c1
DataX_probability_Stack2_c2DataX_classified_Stack2_c2
DataX_probability_Stack2_c3DataX_classified_Stack2_c3
DataX_probability_Stack3_c1DataX_classified_Stack3_c1
DataX_probability_Stack3_c2DataX_classified_Stack3_c2
DataX_probability_Stack3_c3DataX_classified_Stack3_c3
```

- Save your 'probability maps'-substacks and your 'classified images'-substacks each as single files by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Image Sequence*.
- Check the box 'Keep labels' in the dialogue box to add consecutive numbers to your substack file name for labeling the single image files.
- Repeat the segmentation for all of your substacks.
- Create two new folders for the probability maps and the classified images in your directory, in which you can combine all single images from the substacks.

- Copy all single 'probability map'-files of the different substacks into one of the folders and copy all classified image files of the single substacks into the other folder. The order of the files should automatically mirror the order of files in the original pre-processed stack.
- Create a new image stack composed of all substack data for the probability maps by clicking on the tab *File > Import > Image sequence*. A dialogue box opens. Select the folder composed of all single probability maps files, open it and click on the first image file. Click the 'Open'-button to import all images. In the dialogue box 'Sequence Options' check the box 'Convert to 8-bit grayscale', then click the 'OK'-button.
Check in the image stack whether the images are in correct order. If necessary, close the stack, rename images in your input folder to array them in correct order and open the files again in Fiji as a new image stack.
- Open the dialogue box with the properties of the stack by clicking on the tab *Image > Properties* or by pressing [ctrl] + [shift] + [P] on the keyboard instead.
- Enter the voxel depth as a number of pixels for your image stack in the 'Voxel depth' box (e.g. 11 Pixel as a voxel depth should be written as '11.0000' in the box, '1.0000' is the default setting).

Channels (c):

Slices (z):

Frames (t):

Note: c*z*t must equal 10

Unit of length:

Pixel width:

Pixel height:

Voxel depth:

Frame interval:

Origin (pixels):

Global

Click the 'OK'-button to apply the changed properties.

- Save the stack as a TIFF-stack by clicking *File > Save As > Tiff*.
- Repeat the last four steps with the sub-stack data for the classified images.

The results from the segmentation with the TWS-plugin are a TIFF-stack of the probability maps and a TIFF-stack of the classified images.

The classified image stack is the resulting segmented image stack and can be used to create a 3D-model either using the software toolkit Drishti or the Fiji plugin '3D Viewer', as is described in paragraph 6: Computing the 3D Model.

However, for this work further processing of the segmentation results were necessary.

4. Manual correction for false classification

For structures in the images, which have been falsely classified during segmentation with the TWS-plugin, manual correction is necessary. Manual correction can take place either in a later step as a manual removal of structures in the 3D model itself using DrishtiPaint or as a manual removal in the input-data for a 3D-model in Drishti using Fiji.

Here, the second option using Fiji is described first. For removing structures with DrishtiPaint see section 10. *Manual Segmentation using DrishtiPaint*.

Manual correction in Fiji can be performed with the classified image stack and the probability maps stack alike, but is described for the second stack below.

- Open Fiji.
- Open the original pre-processed image stack with Drag&Drop.
- Open the probability maps stack with Drag&Drop.
- Arrange both windows next to each other on the screen and move through both stacks using the scrollbar. Search for falsely classified structures.
- Click on the pipette-icon in the center of the toolbar in the Fiji interface to use the 'Color picker' tool.

- Click on an area in the Probability map that is part of the background, to use the color with which falsely classified structured can be covered. For a probability maps stack, this color should be black (pixel value 255).
- Left-click on the icon for the 'Paintbrush' tool on the left side of the toolbar in the Fiji interface.

- Right-click on the 'Paintbrush' tool icon in the toolbar to adjust the brush width. A dialogue box pops up. Enter the desired brush width as number of pixels, then confirm by clicking the 'OK'-button.
- Left-click on the areas of your probability maps where structures have been falsely classified to add background color with the 'Paintbrush' tool and cover them up.
- To remove the last brushstroke, click on the tab *Edit > Undo* or press [ctrl] + [Z] on the keyboard.
- Save the corrected probability map stack by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*.

Removing all detectable falsely classified structures throughout the a stack is extremely time-consuming. Therefore this method is suited best for removing large structures, which can clearly be identified as falsely classified.

In this work, large areas of ice, which were falsely classified, were removed from the classification.

5. Applying a size filter

An additional size filter can be applied when using the software Ilastik, which computes a segmentation based on the probability map created with the TWS-plugin.

Before applying the size filter, the best threshold value for the segmentation needs to be determined by testing it on a small sample stack.

- Create a folder for the small sample stack in your directory.
- Open Fiji.
- Open the 'probability maps'-stack by using Drag&Drop.
- Click on the tab *Image > Stacks > Tools > Make Substack* to create a small sample substack of probability maps. Enter a range of ten images in the box of the 'Substack Maker' at the desired part of your stack (e.g. '20-30'), then click the 'OK'-button.
- Save the small sample substack of probability maps by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*. Select your new folder for small sample stacks in the directory, enter a name for the file, then click on the 'Save'-button.

As you need to compare the segmentation performed by Ilastik with a certain threshold value with the segmentation performed by the TWS-plugin in Fiji in the next step, the classified images have to serve as input for raw data in Ilastik. Therefore a small sample stack of classified images needs to be created.

- Open the classified image stack in Fiji by using Drag&Drop.
- Click on the tab *Image > Stacks > Tools > Make Substack* to create a small substack of the classified image stack. Enter the **same range of ten images** in the box of the 'Substack Maker' at the desired part of your stack (e.g. '20-30'), then click the 'OK'-button.
- Save the small sample substack of original pre-processed images by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*. Select your new folder for small sample stacks in the directory, enter a name for the file, then click on the 'Save'-button.
- Close Fiji.

Both small sample substacks for probability maps and classified images are needed to determine the most fitting threshold value in Ilastik. The objective of this step is to select a threshold value, with which Ilastik can compute similar segmented images as created with the TWS-plugin.

- Open Ilastik.
- The Ilastik startup screen opens up. Double-click on the project type 'Object classification [Inputs: Raw Data, Pixel Prediction Map]' which is listed under the option 'Create New Project'.
- A dialogue box pops up. Browse through the directory and choose the folder with the small sample substacks to save the project. Enter the project's name and click on the 'Save'-button.
The Ilastik project type 'Object classification [Inputs: Raw Data, Pixel Prediction Map]' opens in a new window.
- In the workflow interface tab *Input data* click on the tab 'Raw Data'. Then click on the '+ Add New'-button to add the classified image stack.

dialogue box opens up. Select the small sample substack for the classified images from the directory and click the 'Open'-button to open the image stack.

- Click on the tab 'Prediction Maps' and subsequently click on the '+ Add'-button in the column 'Nickname'. Select 'Add separate Image(s)'.

- A dialogue box opens up. Select the small sample substack for probability maps from the directory and click the 'Open'-button to open the image stack.
- Click on the tab 'Threshold and Size filter' in the workflow interface to open the filter interface. For the 'Input' value you can choose between channel 0 and channel 1 of the probability map. Select channel 0 as it corresponds to the object probability.

- Change the sigma-values for 'Smooth' in every box to the value '0,0' and the value for the 'Size Filter Min'-box to zero.
- Check the box 'Show intermediate results' on the bottom.

- Try different values for the 'Threshold'-box, while comparing the images from the classified image stack with the images from the probability maps stack.

Switch between stacks by clicking on the 'eye'-icon next to the layer 'Input Channel 0' on the *Layer* interface on the bottom. The visibility of the 'labels'-layer can be turned on and off by clicking on the 'eye'-icon.

- Choose the most fitting 'Threshold'-value, for which the layer 'Input Channel 0' matches the classified objects from the TWS-plugin in the layer 'Raw data' best. Note the 'Threshold'-value to apply it later in the segmentation of your complete image data.
- Save the project by clicking on the tab Project > Save Project or by pressing [ctrl] + [S] on the keyboard.
- Close Ilastik.

Segment the complete image data with Ilastik using the threshold value derived from testing with the small sample substacks and apply a size filter to the segmentation.

If the image data is too large to be segmented by Ilastik, memory errors will occur. If the original pre-processed image stack had to be split into smaller sub-stacks for segmentation with the TWS-plugin, it is likely that this is also necessary for Ilastik.

However, since the results of the segmentation and the pre-processing are by now available as smaller substacks, they can now be used again and fed individually into Ilastik. After segmentation, all sub stacks must be individually mirrored and saved as TIFF files. A combination of these files to a complete image stack is done exactly as already described for the segmentation with the TWS-plugin.

By this means, the sub stacks can be individually segmented and saved with a size filter, as described below for the complete image stack.

- Create a new folder in the directory for the segmented images with a size filter.
- Open Ilastik.
- The Ilastik startup screen opens up. Double-click on the project type 'Object classification [Inputs: Raw Data, Pixel Prediction Map]'.
- A dialogue box pops up. Browse through the directory and choose the folder for the segmented images with the size filter to save the project. Enter the project's name and click on the 'Save'-button.
The Ilastik project type 'Object classification [Inputs: Raw Data, Pixel Prediction Map]' opens in a new window.

- In the workflow interface tab *Input data* click on the tab 'Raw Data'. Then click on the '+ Add New'-button to add the original pre-processed image stack of your image data.
- A dialogue box opens up. Select the original pre-processed image stack from the directory and click the 'Open'-button to open the image stack.
- Click on the tab 'Prediction Maps' and subsequently click on the '+ Add'-button in the column 'Nickname'. Select 'Add separate Image(s)'.
- A dialogue box opens up. Select the small sample substack for probability maps from the directory and click the 'Open'-button to open the image stack.
- Click on the tab *Threshold and Size filter* in the workflow interface to open the filter interface.
- Change the values for 'Smooth' in every box to the value '0,0' and the value for 'Threshold' to the 'Threshold'-value you have derived during testing.
- Apply the size filter by changing the value in the 'Size Filter Min'-box to the minimum pixel size your objects should have in the segmentation. Any objects with an area smaller than this value are not being included in the segmentation.

A useful application of the size filter is the removal of all classified objects whose largest diameter in pixels is smaller than the voxel depth in pixels. Such small objects may not be displayed coherently in a 3D model.

If the objects are approximately circular, you can determine an area for the hypothetical circular shape by taking the voxel depth of the data as the diameter of the circle. The minimum pixel area of the objects for applying the size filter would then be $\pi \cdot (\text{voxel depth}/2)^2$.

- Add two times the number zero to the value in the 'Size filter Max'-box to include large objects in the classification. The new value should be 100 000 000.
- Check the box 'Show intermediate results' on the bottom.
- Click on the 'Apply'-button on the interface.

Selected values in the 'Threshold and size filter'- workflow interface for this work:

Method: simple
 Input: 0
 Smooth: 0,0 ; 0,0 ; 0,0
 Threshold: 0,29 for RWSS, 0,24 for RWSS
 Size filter Min: 95 for RWSN, 65 for RWSS
 Size filter Max: 10000000

- Click on the tab *Object feature selection* in the Ilastik workflow interface to open the *Object feature selection* interface.
- Click on the 'Select features'-button in this interface.

- The dialogue box 'Object feature selection' opens up. Check the box for 'Standard features', then click the 'OK'-button.

You can specify which of the 'Standard Object Features' you want to apply by clicking on the arrow left to the box 'Standard Object Features'. All features included will be listed below and you can remove them from the selection by unchecking their boxes.

- Click on the tab *Object classification* in the workflow interface, to open its interface. Additionally, there are new layers computed and added to the *Layer* interface on the bottom.

- Name the labels in the box 'Label Classes' as the classified objects you are interested in (e.g. 'living roots') by double-clicking on them. To add more labels, click on the '+ Add Label'-button.
- In the Layer interface, click on the 'eye'-icons for 'Binary Image' and 'Prediction' to close the layers. Then click on the 'eye'-icon for the layer 'Objects' to open this layer, which shows the segmented objects.
- Left-click on the first label (yellow) in the 'Label Classes'-box in the *Object Classification* interface. Then click on some of the objects that are marked with different colors on your image throughout the stack in the Z-plane window on the right side, labeling them in yellow. The result should look like the image below, where labeled objects are displayed in yellow and marked with black arrows.

If you are interested in only one type of object, proceed with the next step. Ilastik allows you to distinguish and label different object types. If you need to classify different object classes, repeat this step for all your object classes.

- Click the 'Live update'-button in the *Object Classification* interface, to predict labels for all objects. Check whether all object labels are correctly predicted and whether all objects have been included in the prediction by moving through the image stack in the Z-plane window with the mouse wheel. If necessary, label more and click on the 'Live update'-button again.
- Click on the tab *Object Information Export* in the Ilastik workflow interface to open the interface.

In the 'Export Settings' the default setting for 'Source' is 'Object predictions'. The Object predictions are the segmented image files you want to export. Do not change the export setting for 'Source'.

- Click on the 'Choose Export Image Settings'-button.
- The dialogue box 'Image Export Options' opens up. At 'Transformations' check the box 'Convert to Data Type' and select the option 'unsigned 8-bit' and check the box 'Renormalize [min, max] from'. The default values should here be '0-1' to '0-255' automatically.

- At the 'Output File Info' click on the 'Select'-button. Another dialogue box opens up. Select the folder in the directory in which you want to save the file, then enter a name for the file in the 'File Name'-box. Click the 'Save'-button to confirm your file name and file path and to close the dialogue box.
- Click the 'OK'-button on the bottom of the 'Image Export Options'-dialogue box to confirm the export settings and close the dialogue box.
- Click on the 'Export All'-button in the *Object Information Export* interface to save your object predictions as a HDF5-file in the folder which you have selected in the 'Image Export Options'-dialogue box.

- Click on the tab *Project > Save Project* in the Ilastik interface.
- Close Ilastik.

The object predictions made by Ilastik are a segmented image stack in a HDF5-file format. They need to be loaded into Fiji by using a special plugin in order to save them as a TIFF-file stack, which is needed to compute the 3D model.

Additionally, the HDF5-files created by Ilastik are vertically flipped and need to be re-flipped using Fiji.

- Open Fiji.
- Click on the tab *Help > Update* to open the 'ImageJ Updater'-window. Click on the button 'Manage update sites'.
- Select 'ilastik' in the list of update sites.
- Click on the button 'Apply changes' in the 'ImageJ Updater'.
- Restart Fiji.
- Click on the tab *Plugins > ilastik > Import HDF5* to import the segmented image stack created with Ilastik. The dialogue box 'Select HDF5 file' pops up. Browse for the HDF5-file, then click on the 'Open'-button. A new dialogue box opens up. Check the box 'apply LUT' to use a lookup-table for displaying the file with Fiji. Click the 'OK'-button.

- Check whether the HDF5 image stack is flipped by comparing it with the classified image stack from the TWS-segmentation. Open the classified image stack with the Drag&Drop operation.
To rotate an image stack by 90° for better comparison, click on the tab *Image > Transform > Rotate 90 Degrees Right* or *Rotate 90 Degrees Left*.
- If necessary, re-flip the HDF5 image stack by clicking the tab *Image > Transform > Flip Vertically*. If the image stack was flipped horizontally by Ilastik, click on the tab *Image > Transform > Flip Horizontally* instead.
- Click on the tab *Image > Properties* to open the dialogue box with the properties of the image stack.
- Enter the voxel depth as a number of pixels for your image stack in the 'Voxel depth' box as a number of pixels, then click on the 'OK'-button.
- To change to colors of your binary image-stack to black and white, click in the tab *Image > Adjust > Brightness&Contrast*.
A dialogue box opens up, allowing you to change several parameters. Move the slider bar for 'max.' to the left, then click on the 'Apply'-button. A new dialogue box opens up, asking whether you want to apply the look-up table (LUT) to all stack slices. Confirm by clicking on the 'Yes'-button.
- Change your image stack to white objects on a black background, by inverting your stack. Click on the tab *Edit > Invert*. A dialogue box pops up, asking whether the inversion should be applied on the entire stack. Click on the 'Yes'-button to confirm.
- Save the image stack as TIFF-file by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*.
- Save the image stack as RAW-file by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Raw data*.
- Invert the image stack by clicking on the tab *Edit > Invert*. A dialogue box pops up. Click on the 'yes'-button to confirm the inversion for all slices.
- Save the image stack as TIFF-file by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Tiff*.
- Save the image stack as RAW-file by clicking on the tab *File > Save As > Raw data*.

As a result there are two segmented image stacks with either white objects on a black background or black objects on white background saved both as TIFF-files and as RAW-files.

6. Computing the 3D Model

To compute a simple 3D model from the segmented image data, Fiji contains the plugin '3D Viewer' with which the data can be visualized to gain a first impression of the volume. Large datasets, however, cannot be processed well by the plugin, therefore the software Drishti should be used for volume rendering.

- Open Fiji.
- Import your image stack by clicking on the tab *File > Open*, then choose your TIFF-file with white objects on a black background from the directory and click 'OK'.

If necessary, invert your image stack to get white objects by clicking on the tab *Image > Invert*.

- Click on the tab *Image > Properties* to check whether your image stack has the correct voxel depth for your model. If not, change the voxel depth, then confirm by clicking on the 'OK'-button.
- Click on the tab *Plugins > 3D Viewer*. The dialogue box 'Add' opens up.

You may name your 3D model in the box for 'Name'.

In the box for 'Display as' select 'Volume'.

Changing the default settings for 'Threshold' and 'Resampling factor' is not necessary.

Choose a color (e.g. 'Magenta'), then click on the 'OK'-button.

The 3D viewer opens up, displaying your volume. You can change its orientation by dragging it with your left mouse pointer. Different filters can be applied by right-clicking on the volume and choosing from the menu opening up.

Although Fiji provides a plugin for displaying 3D models, the software package Drishti is much more suited for this task as it had been explicitly designed for the purpose of volume rendering. Additionally, Fiji has been observed to crash while processing large image data with the plugin '3D Viewer'.

Visualizing the segmented image data with Drishti is therefore the option which is preferable to the '3D Viewer'-plugin, as Drishti is far superior to the plugin.

To display the data as a volume with Drishti, the data needs to be converted into a pvl.nc-file using the software Drishtimport first.

Being a freeware software, the newest version (currently v.2.6.5) is not necessarily working correctly at all times yet, especially while dealing with large image data. It is advised to use the second newest version for conversion of your data into pvl.nc-files, as it is not going to crash while converting large data sets.

- Open Drishtimport v.2.6.4 from the folder installed for Drishti version 2.6.4.
- Click on the tab *Files > Load > Files > RAW files*.
- A dialogue box opens up. Select the RAW-stack with white objects on a black background in the directory, then click the 'Open'-button.
- The dialogue box 'Load Raw Plugin Dialog' opens up. In the box 'Voxel Type' select 'unsigned byte' and for the box 'Grid size' fill in the dimensions of your stack in the order 'z y x', 'z' being the number of images the stack contains, 'y' being the height of the images in pixels and 'x' being the width of the images in pixels. In between the numbers leave a blank space to separate them from each other. Click on the 'OK'-button.

- The dialogue box 'Histogram ?' opens up. Select 'yes', which should be the default setting, then click on the 'OK'-button.

- The file you want to import is now displayed in Drishtimport. Check whether the image stack has been imported correctly by moving through the stack using the scrollbar on the left side in the lower box.

- Click on the tab *File > Save As (S)*. A dialogue box pops up. Select a folder in the directory in which the file should be saved. Save the file as a pvl.nc-file by clicking on the 'OK'-button.
- The dialogue box 'Save Data?' opens up. Click on the 'OK'-button to confirm 'Yes' as the default setting and to save slice 0 as the top slice.

- The dialogue box 'Save Processed Volume?' pops up. Click on the 'OK'-button to confirm 'No' as the default setting.

- The dialogue box 'Volume Size?' opens up. Click on the 'OK'-button to confirm the default setting for 'No subsampling in Z'.

- The dialogue box 'Final Volume?' pops up. Check whether the values for the dimensions 'z y x' are in order and of correct pixel size. Click on the 'OK'-button to confirm the settings.

- The dialogue box 'Additional Information' pops up. For the box 'Voxel Units' select the option 'no units'. In the box 'Voxel Size' change the values from '0 0 0' to the values for the 'x y z' dimensions of a voxel from the image stack. Note that the order is reversed from the 'Grid Size' in the second dialogue box! Start with entering the voxel width, followed by height and finally depth in pixel numbers (e.g. 1 1 9.12). Leave a blank space between the values to separate them from each other. Remaining options in the dialogue box should be left in the default setting. Confirm the settings by clicking on the 'OK'-button.

- Wait for DrishtiImport has finished converting the image stack into the pvl.nc-file, then close DrishtiImport.

The resulting pvl.nc-file is a 3D model of the original image stack. It can be imported into Drishti v.2.6.5 as the newest version of Drishti and displayed as a volume.

- Open Drishti v.2.6.5.
- Click on the tab *File > Load Volume > Load 1 Volume*.

- A dialogue box opens up. Select the pvl.nc-file of the image stack from the directory and click on the 'OK'-button.
- To display the voxel depth in the model, switch to 'Raycast mode' by pressing [F3] on the keyboard.
- A dialogue box pops up. Confirm the default setting 'Subsampling Level: 1' by clicking on the 'OK'-button.

The pvl.nc-file of the stack is displayed as a volume in Drishti. If problems with the voxel size occur, they can be edited manually.

- Check, whether the volume's dimensions are correctly displayed. Click on the tab *View > Volume Information* and change the voxel size in the corresponding box to adjust the model if necessary.

7. Volume Rendering

It is possible that the volume is not visible after loading it into Drishti. This problem can be solved by choosing a fitting transfer function with the 'Transfer Function Editor'.

The transfer function should in any case be modified for volume rendering in order to create a fixed appearance of the final image. With suitable rendering the volume is displayed more distinctly, for instance in different shades of color.

- To render the volume and change the transfer function, use the 'Transfer Function Editor' interface. Click on the 'New'-button to create a new transfer function.
- Check the box 'TF1' (Transfer Function 1) to select the new transfer function.
- Change the range of pixel values from your data in the diagram below. As it is an 8-bit image-stack, values range from 0 – 255. Any value included in the pixel range between the two points is displayed in the model.
- Change the colors of the volume in the diagram with the checkerboard-background on the bottom of the 'Transfer Function Editor' interface.

- Double-click on any of the three points to change its color. The dialogue box 'Select color ?' open ups. Move the bar around the color wheel to choose a color and select a hue by clicking on the circles in the center. Click on the 'OK'-button to apply the change.

- Drag the points on the graph to different locations on the pixel range, to determine which pixel values are displayed in the color of the point.
- Drag the points on the graph up or down to either increase or decrease their color intensity displayed in the volume.

- Add points to the graph by left-clicking on the graph where you want to insert a point for more color variation.

- Remove points from the graph by right-clicking on them.

The volume should be displayed in the selected colors. The model can be examined more closely by moving it within the Drishti main interface, currently in 'Raycast mode'.

- Remove or add the bounding box by pressing [b] on the keyboard.
- Zoom into the volume by moving the mouse-wheel forward.
- Zoom out of the volume by moving the mouse-wheel backwards.

- Move the volume up, down or sideways by pressing the right mouse-button while moving the volume in the desired direction.
- Start automatic rotation of the volume by left-clicking on the model and simultaneously exerting a small spin with the mouse pointer. The volume will start rotating around its center point.
- Rotate the volume manually by pressing the left mouse-button and moving the mouse.
- Display only selected parts of your model by decreasing the size of the bounding box. Move the mouse pointer to the centre of one side of the bounding box where its diagonal lines cross until the side you want to crop the volume turns red. Hold down

the left mouse button and move the mouse wheel to move the bounding box side. In this way, the bounding box can be reduced in size, whereupon the volume in its representation is also reduced.

- To change the background color of the volume, click on the tab *View > Preferences*. The 'Preferences'-interface opens up. Click on the 'background color'-button and select the new background color from the dialogue box, which opens up. Apply the new color by clicking on the 'OK'-button.

In the raycast mode, other changes for the display of the volume in Drishti can be made regarding the illumination of the model.

- Use the 'Raycast menu' that has opened up by pressing [F3] to apply changes. If it has been accidentally closed, open it again by clicking on the tab *View > Raycast mode*.
- Change the ray depth for the illumination of the volume by clicking on the 'Ray Depth'-tab and by moving the scrollbar to a different value (0-100).
- Change the size of the shadows within the volume by clicking on the 'Shadow'-tab and by moving the scrollbar to a new value (0-10).

Additionally, you may adjust the lighting settings for rendering by using the 'shader widget'.

- Click on the tab *View > Shader Widget* to open the 'Shader Widget' window.

- Adjust the lighting settings to your preferences (e.g. reduce 'ambient' and 'specular' while increasing 'diffuse' to a maximum for high contrasts).

8. Basic animation

Once you have rendered your volume, you can use Drishti to produce single image files of your volume (snapshots) or images series and movies using the 'Keyframe Editor'. To increase the image quality for your basic animation, increase the texture memory size and image quality for Drishti.

- Click on the tab View > Preferences to open the 'Preferences' window.

- In 'Tab 1', increase the image quality by moving the all bars for both 'Texture Memory Size' and 'Image quality' to the far right.

- Click on the tab File > Save Image to save a single image file. The dialogue box 'Image Size?' opens up. Click on the 'OK'-button to confirm the default setting.

A dialogue box pops up in which you can name the image file and select the folder in which it will be saved. Click on the 'Save'-button to save your image.

The dialogue box 'Image Type?' opens up, confirm the default setting 'Mono Image' by clicking 'OK'.

To create a movie or image series of your volume, you need to determine 'Keyframes' of your rendered volume. A 'frame' is understood as a snapshot within a movie or image series. When certain key-frames are set by the operator, Drishti can automatically generate more frames in between to create a continuous series or movie.

- Click on the tab View > KeyFrame Editor to open the 'KeyFrame Editor' window.

- Move your rendered volume to the desired starting orientation with your mouse.
- In the 'KeyFrame Editor' click on the button 'Set Keyframe' to save the orientation of your rendered volume as 'Frame 1'.
- Edit the volume by slightly changing the orientation of your volume in the 3D viewer window to your desired second frame, then click on a new position on the frame axis in the 'KeyFrame Editor' and click on the button 'Set Keyframe' to save the orientation of the volume as 'Frame 2'.
- Continue setting keyframes until you have enough to show your 3D-model in detail. For a slow rotation in a movie it is recommended to place the keyframes at least 90 units apart from each other on the frame axis.
- Click on the tab *File > Save movie* to create a movie from your keyframes as a wmv-file. A dialogue box opens up. Manually change the resolution by increasing both numbers to a value which is a multiple of 16, then click 'OK'.
- A new dialogue box pops up. Name your file and browse the directory for a folder to save it in. Click on the 'Save'-button.
- Another dialogue box opens up. Leave the settings for 'Frame steps' at the default value '1' by clicking on the 'OK'-button.
- A last dialogue box pops up. You can define the frame rate by changing the number in the box. A high frame rate (e.g. 40) leads to many images between each key frame, resulting in a slow movie, in which your volume rotates evenly. Confirm your settings by clicking on the 'OK'-button.

9. Mesh Generation

Meshes of the entire volume can be generated using either Drishti or DrishtiPaint. However, it is recommended to use DrishtiPaint for mesh generation, as the results are better and when performing segmentation with DrishtiPaint, one or several tags can be extracted separately as a mesh.

Mesh generation using Drishti is described first.

- Open Drishti v.2.6.5.
- Click on the tab *File > Load Volume > Load Volume 1*. Browse the directory to open the pvl.nc-file, then click on the 'Open'-button.
- Press [F3] on your keyboard to switch to raycast-mode.
- Expand the range of your transfer function to the maximum by moving the slider bar in the 'Transfer Function Editor' to the right end.
- Click on the tab *Plugins > Mesh Generator*, to generate a mesh of the entire volume. The dialogue box 'Mesh Generation Parameters' opens up. Confirm the default settings by clicking 'OK'.

The dialogue box 'Use memory?' pops up. Enter the maximum memory your operational systems allows you to use in the box.

The dialogue box 'Export mesh to file' opens. Choose a folder in your directory, name your file and save it as a ply-file by clicking on the 'Save'-button.

Alternatively, DrishtiPaint can be used to create a mesh of either the entire volume, segmented parts of it or substacks from the volume.

- Open DrishtiPaint v.2.6.5.
- Click on the tab *File > Load* and choose your pvl.nc-file or your mask.pvl.nc-file, in case you have performed segmentation on the volume with DrishtiPaint beforehand. Click 'OK' to open it in DrishtiPaint
- Expand the range of your transfer function to the maximum by moving the slider bar in the 'Transfer Function Editor' to the right end.
- Render your volume by choosing colors for the transfer function in the 'Transfer Function Editor'.
- Click on the tab *File > Mesh Tagged Region*. The dialogue box 'Save Mesh for Tag?' opens up, offering different options for tags to be generated as a mesh.

- To create a mesh of the entire volume, choose '-2' to mesh whatever is visible at the moment.
- To generate a mesh only consisting of specific segmented objects, choose their tag (e.g. '2'). Confirm your choice by clicking 'OK'.

- The dialogue box 'Color Mesh with?' pops up. Choose 'Transfer function', then click on the 'OK'-button.
- The dialogue box 'Voxel scaling?' opens up. Confirm the default setting 'yes' by clicking 'OK'.
- The dialogue box 'Level of Details' pops up. For 'Subsampling level for mesh generation' choose '1', then click on the 'OK'-button.
- The dialogue box 'Close holes?' opens up. Choose '1' for the box 'Close Holes of Size', then click 'OK'.

- The dialogue box 'Apply data smoothing before meshing' pops up. Choose '0' to avoid any smoothing and click on the 'OK'-button.

- The dialogue box 'Apply mesh smoothing' opens up. Choose '2', to apply a little smoothing, then click on the 'OK'-button.
- A dialogue box opens up, asking you to choose a folder in the directory to save the extracted mesh. Name your file and save it as a ply-file by clicking on the 'Save'-button.

Meshes can be opened using different open-source software such as blender, Autodesk® Meshmixer™ or MeshLab. With these programs, many operations can be performed on the meshes, including volume and surface area measurements, coloring, further smoothing, deforming or 3D printing.

10. Volume calculation

Volume calculation of the 3D model can be performed using both Drishti and the Fiji command 'Analyse particles'. Additionally, software such as MeshLab or Autodesk® Meshmixer™ is able to calculate a the volume of meshes generated with Drishti.

For the volume calculation of the 3D model, different versions of Drishti offer different solutions, for which instructions are given in the following paragraphs.

The latest version Drishti v.2.6.5 can calculate the volume and the surface area of the model in raycast mode, if the operational system holds sufficient computing power in the graphics card.

- Open Drishti v.2.6.5 and load your data as a pvl.nc-file.
- Switch to raycast-mode by pressing [F3] on the keyboard.

Drishti can calculate the surface area and the volume that is currently displayed in the 3D viewer. As your input data consists of a binary image stack and Drishti uses linear interpolation to display the volume, the linear interpolation function needs to be turned off before the calculation can be performed.

- Click on the tab *Toogle > Linear Interpolation* to de-select the interpolation. Since your input stack is binary, the 3D model will vanish from the 3D viewer window, because its values are not covered by the transfer function anymore.
- Expand the transfer function to the pixel value of 255 by moving the bar in the 'Transfer Function Editor' to the maximum on the right. The 3D-model will be displayed again.

- Click on the tab *Functions > Measurements > Volume* in the main Drishti interface to calculate the volume of the model.
The dialogue box 'Get Volume?' pops up, showing the default setting '-1' for 'Tag value'. Confirm the default setting by clicking 'OK'.

A dialogue box opens up, showing the overall number of voxels in the model and their volume. As your volume has no assigned unit, you need to calculate the volume of one voxel and simply multiply it with the number of voxels derived from Drishti.

- Click on the tab *Functions > Measurements > Surface Area* in the main Drishti interface to calculate the surface area of the model.

For this work, however, a different approach was used to try to calculate the volume of each model using the older version DrishtiPaint v.2.6.3, since the dataset was too large to be processed with the available hardware in the latest version of Drishti. However, the volume data obtained differed strongly from all other volumetric measurements result and this function cannot be recommended.

- Open DrishtiPaint v.2.6.3.
- Click on the tab *File > Load* to import your data. Choose the pvl.nce-file from the directory and click on the 'Open'-button. The dialogue box 'Subsampling?' opens up. Select '1', which should be the default setting, and click 'OK'.
- In the 'Transfer Function Editor' window, expand the transfer function to the value 255 by moving the bar to the right end.
- Press the spacebar on the keyboard to open the 'Command Help'-window.

'getvolume', then click on the 'OK'-button. A dialogue box opens up, showing '-1' for the default setting of 'Tag Value'. Click on the 'OK'-button to confirm the setting.

A dialogue box opens up, showing the overall number of voxels in the model and their volume. As your volume has no assigned unit, you need to calculate the volume of one voxel and simply multiply it with the number of voxels derived from Drishti.

If both approaches to calculate the volume of the 3D model in Drishti fail due to a lack of computing power, try to divide your model into smaller models.

Use Fiji to create substacks of your input data, as has been described in detail above (tab: *Image > Stacks > Tools > Make Substack*) and save them as RAW-files. Use DrishtiImport to convert these RAW-files into pvl.nc-files, which you can load into Drishti and proceed with the volume calculation.

A different and more detailed approach for volume calculation is using the Fiji command 'Analyze Particles', which measures the area of a pixel class for entire image stacks in pixels. You can convert the result into the desired unit (e.g. mm) and only need to multiply it with the mean distance between each cut, which is simply your voxel depth. As a result, you obtain volume information for each image of your stack, creating detailed volume information.

- Open Fiji.
- Click on the tab *File > Import > TIFF*. Choose your segmented (and possibly size filtered) image stack containing black objects on a white background in the directory and click on the 'Open'-button.

You may also invert your stack of white objects on a black background by clicking on the tab *Edit > Invert*, then confirm the conversion to the entire stack. Fiji will analyze only black objects on a white background with the 'Analyze Particles' command.

- Click on the tab *Analyze > Analyze Particles*. The 'Analyze Particles' dialogue box opens up.

Select 'Outlines' for the box 'Show' and check the boxes for 'Display results' and 'Summarize', then click on the 'OK'-button. (You may also try checking the 'Include holes' box to include holes within the objects of your segmentation in the calculation).

- The dialogue box 'Process stack?' pops up. Click on the 'OK'-button to process the entire stack.

- The three new windows 'Results', 'Summary of...' and 'Drawing of...' will open. Fiji has labeled each object (particle) in each image and created an image stack consisting of the drawn outlines of the particles and their label in red.

Check in the 'Drawing of ...' image stack, whether Fiji has detected the black objects correctly.

The 'Summary of ...' window contains a spreadsheet listing all slices, the number of objects detected ('Count'), their total area and their average size in pixels in each slide and the percentage of area covered per slice.

File Edit Font						
Slice	Count	Total Area	Average Size	%Area	Mean	
444,0 mm	9107	506866	55.657	17.027	0	
444,5 mm	9273	477252	51.467	16.032	0	
445,0 mm	9891	473259	47.847	15.898	0	
445,5 mm	9900	473164	47.794	15.895	0	
446,0 mm	9391	468694	49.909	15.745	0	
446,5 mm	9808	473141	48.240	15.894	0	
447,0 mm	9627	521296	54.149	17.512	0	
447,5 mm	9485	533888	56.288	17.935	0	
448,0 mm	9793	535090	54.640	17.975	0	

The table from 'Summary of...' can be saved as a csv-file and opened in a spreadsheet software such as LibreOffice Calc or Microsoft Excel to calculate the sum of total area for the stack, which then can be multiplied by the voxel depth to calculate the volume.

- In the 'Summary of...' window, click on the tab *File > Save As* to save the table as a csv-file. Choose a name and a folder in the directory, then click the 'Save'-button.

Alternatively, MeshLab can be used to calculate the Volume of meshes created with DrishtiPaint. In this work, volume measurements with MeshLab were carried out on adjusted substacks of RWSS, which represented the slab size from manual washing and sieving for volume comparison.

- Open MeshLab
- Click on the tab *File > Import Mesh*. A dialogue box opens up. Browse your directory and choose your PLY-file. Click on the 'Open'-button.
- In the MeshLab toolbar, click on the button with the symbol of the magnifying glass to open the search window.
- Enter 'Compute Geometric Measures' and click on the tab offered by the search function.

Mesh Lab now starts calculating different geometric measures such as surface area and volume of the mesh. Results are displayed in the bottom window on the left.

- Use the scroll bar to scroll down in the window until you find the measures for 'Volume'.

11. Manual Segmentation using DrishtiPaint

If you have decided to segment single objects from your volume rendered with Drishti, DrishtiPaint allows for manual segmentation to create smaller sub-volumes, that contain only the desired object. For instance, you can use DrishtiPaint to create a volume of only one single structure like a certain root, if you need to observe a certain structure within your volume.

DrishtiPaint allows you to do manual slice by slice segmentation and to paint on the slices, applying different colors to different structures.

- Open DrishtiPaint v.2.6.5.
- Click on the tab *Load > Volume* in the DrishtiPaint interface to choose the pvl.nc-file you want to segment from the directory or simply drag and drop the file into the DrishtiPaint window.

While loading your volume, DrishtiPaint creates two different files, which are saved in the same folder as your input data. One is a mask-file in which your segmentation is stored, the other is a mask.pvl.nc-file, which is the header-file for the mask-file. If you want to open the segmented project in DrishtiPaint again, use the mask-file.

- Expand the windows for the Z-plane of the image stack and the 3D-view to the right.
- Expand the range of the transfer function in the 'Transfer Function Editor' window to include the value 255 by moving the scrollbar to the maximum right.
- Click on the tab *View > Color Editor* to open the 'Color Editor' window. In the 'Color Editor' there are tags ranging from 0 to 255. 'Tag0' represents the original value of a pixel from your image stack and is not a segmentation. 'Tag1' to 'tag255' are available for you to apply on the image stack and to 'tag' objects with as a manual segmentation.

Different colors for the tags can be chosen either by choosing individual colors for each tag or applying a gradient of colors on all tags.

- Double click on a tag color to apply a color for the individual tag. A dialogue box opens up and you may choose a color from a color wheel.
- Click on the button 'New Tag Colors' in the 'Color Editor' and choose a type of color gradient or alternatively random colors to apply on all tags.

Single structures are tagged in the Z-plane window of the images stack and can be painted with the differently colored tags.

- Left-click on the tag you want to apply or choose its number in the 'Tag' box in the 'Seg Param' window.
- Paint on the object by pressing the left mouse button and dragging the mouse over the object. The background is not being painted, since it is not included in the transfer function.
- Erase a tag color by pressing the right mouse button.
- Move from slice to slice by using the mouse wheel, the arrow keys on the keyboard or the slider bar in the Z-plane window.

The color on the painted region is not set yet for the program, to allow for corrections. Once a color is set, it will appear in the next slice in a darker shade, enabling you to trace an object through the Z-plane.

- Press [p] on the keyboard to truly apply the paint on the objects in the painted region on a certain slice, in this way tagging the object.
- Press [esc] to remove all tag colors of previous slices from your current slice, thus erasing the 'trace' of an object. Regularly remove such 'traces' to avoid falsely tagging objects by accident. New objects appearing in a new slice in the area of the 'trace' will be automatically painted on with your current tag color and will be tagged once you press [p].
- Press [r] on the keyboard to remove the applied tag color from a slice.
- Press a capital [P] on your keyboard to apply a tag to several slices. A dialogue box opens, in which either 'forward' or 'backward' as a direction in the Z-plane for the operation can be chosen.

- Press [shift] and use the left mouse button to tag a region as background. Thereby it is excluded from automatic tagging.
- Click on the tab *Help* to learn all keyboard shortcuts necessary to navigate DrishtiPaint. A dialogue box opens up, listing the keyboard shortcuts.

The tagged region can be saved as a pvl.nc-file to be loaded into Drishti.

- Click on the tab *File > Extract Tagged Region* to create a volume file solely consisting of segmented objects which were tagged in DrishtiPaint.

The dialogue box 'Extract volume data for Tag' opens up. Choose the tag numbers you want to extract, then click on the 'OK'-button.

The dialogue box 'Extract Data' opens up. Choose 'Tag only' or 'Tag + Transfer Function', then click 'OK'.

The dialogue box 'Outside Value' pops up. Confirm the default setting '0' by clicking on the 'OK'-button.

The dialogue box 'Save volume' opens up. Browse the directory and select the folder in which you want to save the extracted volume. Name the file and click on the 'Save'-button.

The segmented objects can also be extracted as a mesh and saved as ply-file to calculate their volume separately.

Single subvolumes can be loaded into Drishti and different measurements of the volume can be carried out (e.g. length or angle of a structure). For this it is necessary to manually add points to your volume.

- Open Drishti v. 2.6.5.
- Drag&Drop the pvl.nc-file of your volume into the main window to open your volume.

- Left click and press [shift] to add a point on your volume.
As you need at least two points to create a path for length measurements, add a second or more points.

Points can be deleted by opening the 'Command Help' window (press [space]) and entering the command 'removepoints all' or 'removepoints selected'.

For length measurements, you need to create a path between points.

- Press the space-bar and open the 'Command Help'-window. Choose 'path' in the box on the right side or type in 'path' in the box on the bottom left. Confirm your command by clicking on the 'OK'-button.
- Move the mouse over the path to see the length in pixels (or the length in any unit you choose for your volume).

- Move the path by re-arranging it with the mouse to change its course.

- Delete the path by pressing [Del] and left-clicking on the path.

For angle measurements you need to add three points in the correct order, making your second point the center of your angle.

- Add three points by pressing [shift] and clicking left.
- Press [space] to open the 'Command Help'-window. Type in 'getangle' as the command in the bottom left box. Confirm by clicking on the 'OK' button.

